

Experimental Investigation on Energy Absorbing Pressurised Composite Tubes

T.Hou¹, B.G.Prusty¹, G.Pearce¹, D.Kelly¹ and R. Thomson^{2,3}

¹ School of Mechanical and Manufacturing Engineering, University of New South Wales, Sydney, Australia

² Cooperative Research Centre for Advanced Composite Structures, Fishermans Bend, Australia

³ Advanced Composite Structures Australia Pty Ltd, Fishermans Bend, Australia

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Abstract

This paper details the validation through experimental investigation of a novel variable load concept capable of improving energy absorbing structures. Quasi-static crush testing was conducted with pressurised carbon-fibre/epoxy specimens representative of elements in an energy absorbing structure. The results show that the crushing force can be controlled and so that pressurised composite elements can be fully expended under a range of crash scenarios. The research also demonstrates that an adaptive energy absorber can be designed using pressurised composite tubes in which the initial internal pressure and the release speed of internally compressed air are controlled.

1. Introduction

In aerospace industries, the crashworthiness performance of rotorcraft structures is very important to the occupants. The main objective of designing crashworthy aerospace structures is to absorb maximum energy with minimum weight, while lowering the peak loads transmitted to occupants to be within human tolerance. Metallic thin-walled structures with different cross-sections have been used since 1970s [1-3]. In recent years, there has been considerable interest in use of composite materials for the crashworthiness, driven mainly by the increasing use of these materials for the primary structure of aerospace industry. In addition, the laminated composite structures can offer vast potential for optimally tailoring a design to the applied loading, which in turn results in an energy absorbing structure with increased strength and stiffness compared to the traditional metallic constructions. Therefore, intensive work has been carried out to examine the energy absorption performance and failure mechanism of open and

closed sections made out of composite materials [4-11].

One of the concepts used to improve the performance of energy absorbing structures is to achieve adaptive energy absorption. For example, a MR damper was tested by Crzegorz and Holnicki [12] as an adaptive impact absorber for helicopter landing gear. Although controllable resistant force can be achieved in this kind of damper, it can only work at low velocity and there are still many unsolved issues for their application under impact loadings. In a second example, Abosbaia et al. [10] investigated the energy absorption of segmented composite tubes, which consisted of three types of fibre reinforcement types, under quasi-static compressive loading. This segmentation concept integrated into composite crush tubes has shown the potential of variable load behaviour in different crush stages during the test, but the crush force efficiency (defined as steady state crushing stress over peak crushing force) was very poor with these tests. The tested concept showed a change in segmentation sequence affects the crush loads significantly and some segmented tubes failed with early buckling and catastrophic failure. The crush tubes without triggering mechanisms led to the crush progressing from both sides of the energy absorber. The design would therefore be incapable of reacting in a controlled manner as a crashworthiness structure. The segmented composite tubes investigated by Abosbaia et al.[10] are therefore less efficient than the integrated radius triggering mechanisms reported in this paper.

The current work in this paper forms part of the Cooperative Research Centre for Advanced Composite Structures (CRC-ACS) project "Systems for Crashworthiness". As part of this project, a novel variable load concept to improve the performance of the energy absorption of a crushing composite element was developed for helicopter crashworthiness applications. This variable load concept will be presented with details in the next section. The primary aims of the experimental test program reported in this paper were to investigate

the effect of triggering radius size on the energy absorption capabilities of circular cross section tubes and evaluate pressurised composite tubes in order to prove the variable load concept. Both quasi-static (5 mm/min) and high speed (900 mm/min) tests were conducted and the influence on the energy absorption and crushing were investigated. As an outcome of this work, a crushing system which is capable for pressurised composites testing was developed.

Failure by progressive crushing differs from catastrophic failure modes in that it offers the most effective and efficient mode of energy absorption and, in general, circular-section tubes provide the optimum geometrical form [13]. Therefore, circular shape tubes have been widely used in the investigation of crashworthiness structures [4, 5, 7, 10, 14-16]. A limited amount of work using composite materials has been reported by Thornton [11, 17] for square section tubes. In the current research, circular-section tubes will be selected for the investigation because it is easier to seal a circular section to maintain internal pressure.

2. Variable load concept

A novel variable load concept was developed and coupled with a device developed in this work, which can be used to optimally absorb energy during a vehicle crash event, minimising the harm to occupants by applying the ideal deceleration for the specific crash speed.

Typically energy absorbers expend crash energy by crushing at a constant load over a variable stroke (crushing distance). The deceleration of the occupants is therefore constant regardless of the crash velocity. The result is under-utilisation of the crushing stroke if the crash speed is too low; leading to inefficient material usage and occupants experiencing unnecessarily high deceleration. Alternatively, if the crash speed is too high, the crushing stroke is exhausted and the tube “bottoms out”, leading to very high peak loads experienced by the occupants, as indicated in Fig. 1a.

With this variable load concept, the energy absorber is designed to crush with a variable load and constant stroke. In this case the occupant never experiences unduly high decelerations because the energy absorber stroke is always optimally utilised, regardless of the crash scenario. The result is minimisation of peak forces experienced by the occupants and the lowest possible risk of injury or death, as shown in Fig. 1b. In addition, if a variable load energy absorber is used under the seat, crushing can also be adjusted based on the occupant mass. This can solve the issue that lower mass occupant experience higher accelerations for a constant force energy absorber.

Two loading types have been included in this investigation. The first type is to optimise the tube design for a particular mass and impact velocity, whereas, the second type allows a controllable crushing force to achieve an adaptable crushing element that can be fully expended under a range of accident scenarios.

Fig. 1. Load-displacement curves for an energy absorber (a) passive design (b) with variable crushing load

3. Experimental testing

3.1 Specimen description

Axi-symmetric cylindrical tubes have been preferred by researchers to carry out experimental work on the energy absorption of composite materials because they are easy to fabricate and also close to the geometry of the actual crashworthy structures [18]. Beside this, circular cross section composite tubes were selected in this work, because it is easier to seal the compressed air inside the device than for other closed section energy absorbing structures, such as square shape cross section tubes. The noncircular sections can experience leakage from the corners and the pressurisation can cause stress concentrations located at the corners.

Composite tubes were initially manufactured by wrapping a woven thermoplastic prepreg material onto a mandrel with a pure 0°/90° lay-up and then cured in an autoclave according to the manufacturer’s specification. The prepreg material that was used is ‘SKY FLEX WSN-3K’, a plain-weave fabric that features carbon fibre material and epoxy resin, see Table 2. The specimens were then cut into the geometry shown in Fig. 2. The composite tube is 120.0 mm in length, wall thickness (t) 1 mm with inner diameter (D) 38.2 mm. A 70° chamfer was machined into one end of each specimen.

In order to achieve a large range of force in the profiles in Fig. 1b, the first step is to achieve crushing behaviour as low as possible for the low

impact energy case. Though the Specific Energy Absorption (SEA) increases with decreasing diameter (D) of the tube, SEA mainly depends on the absolute value of thickness (t), rather than the D/t ratio. For a given value of D , SEA increases with increasing t up to certain value and it starts to decrease above that. Highest specific energy absorption capability has been displayed by tubes of thickness in the range of 2-3mm[19]. To achieve a low force, the lowest thickness of tubes is preferred while avoiding buckling failure. Gupta et al. [20] reported that the catastrophic failure and global buckling of axially crushed composite circular cross section tubes can be avoided by maintaining the D/t ratio between 15 and 40. Thus the wall thickness of crushing element has been carefully selected to be 1 mm with D/t ratio approximately 38. Note that a triggering mechanism is also used to ensure the lower impact energy profile.

Table 1
Test matrix.

Specimen Designation	Quasi-static /High speed	Internal pressure	No. of specimens
<i>Tubes straight trigger mechanism</i>			
S0-T1-0	QS	0	3
S0-T1-9	QS	9	3
S0-T1-18	QS	18	3
<hr/>			
D0-T1-0	HS	0	3
D0-T1-9	HS	9	3
D0-T1-18	HS	18	3
<hr/>			
<i>Tubes with 6 mm trigger mechanism</i>			
S6-T1-0	QS	0	3
S6-T1-9	QS	9	3
S6-T1-18	QS	18	3
<hr/>			
D6-T1-0	HS	0	3
D6-T1-9	HS	9	3
D6-T1-18	HS	18	3

Fig. 2. Crush composite tubes.

Table 2

Properties of composite materials.

Manufacturer	Architecture	Material	Density (kg/m ³)	Ply thickness (mm)	Material strength		
					Tensile (MPa)	Compressive (MPa)	Shear (Mpa)
Exel	Woven Fabric	Carbon/epoxy prepreg	1500	0.24	800	750	80

3.2 Test rig and experiment setup

A crushing test system has been developed, as shown in Fig. 3, to conduct both quasi-static and high speed experiments. To overcome the sealing problem, a special plug impactor and crushing base have been designed with a triggering mechanism and sealing zone, which can initiate the composite tube into progressive crushing mode and also simultaneously seal the air inside the tube during the crushing process. Double O-rings are chosen for sealing on both top and bottom plug-in tools to ensure a good seal and balance the friction between the composite tube and the plugs. A lower friction force from crushing at the top may lead to initiation of crushing of the tube from the top instead of from the triggering mechanism. The base includes three channels. These are a releasing outlet, an air inlet and another channel connected to a pressure transducer with maximum range at 50 bar. The base can be used to fill compressed air into the system through a hand pump as shown in **Error! Reference source not found.** and also controls the pressure relieved during the test. The inlet valve is a one-way valve and thus it can prevent air from flowing out of the system. The release valve also works as a safety valve to avoid the internal pressure rising too high.

3.3 Test method

Quasi-static testing is less expensive than high speed dynamic testing and the investigation under quasi-static conditions can provide good qualitative assessment as to the operation of the crushing system. The test results can be used to prove the variable load concept demonstrated in Fig. 1.

Quasi-static testing was therefore conducted in an Instron 8805 universal 250 kN machine at 5 mm/min. As dynamic/impact testing will be conducted in future, the secondary aim of current

study is to gain a better understanding of the crushing characteristics of the new energy absorbing system being investigated. Higher crushing speed crushing was also performed at 900 mm/min, which is as the maximum test speed can be achieved with the available test machine.

During this test program, the composite tubes were pre-pressurised and loaded in compression. For each configuration of the triggering mechanism, three different constant pressure levels were maintained by using the relief valve. In this work, the pressure levels used were 9 bar and 18 bar and the results were compared with the tubes crushed without any pressurisation. Each of the tubes was crushed to 45 mm stroke length to investigate the energy absorbing behaviour and the variable load concept was validated from these results.

Fig. 3. Experiment set-up.

4. Results and discussion

The specific energy absorption of pressurised composite tubes was investigated under two crushing rates, quasi-static (5 mm/min) and high speed (900 mm/min). Internal pressure was monitored during the tests to identify any possible leakage. The results show that the double O-ring sealing system is capable of sealing compressed air dynamically inside the composite tubes. Typical pressure profiles are presented for quasi-static and high speed tests in Fig. 4. Note that the relative pressure is reported in this study, which means the ambient pressure is at 0 bar. The release valve is functioning with a spring, thus there is limitation of the sensitivity and accuracy of the device. The valve was set with certain tolerance at a lower level than the desired pressure before each test. The pressure initially built up with the specimen stroke around 2.0 mm and it began to stabilise after the desired pressure level was reached. Note that there is a pressure overshoot in Fig. 4 (R) for the 18 bar high speed test. This is due to the fact that the inertial force from the mass of the spring prevented the valve from opening quickly enough when the internal pressure increased rapidly. Therefore, a low

inertia diaphragm pressure regulator is being considered for future higher speed impact tests.

A wide range of steady state crushing force is required to achieve the most effective crushing system with variable load concept in a crash scenario. The lower level of Steady State Crush Force (SSCF) can be achieved by introducing a relatively large trigger radius with a thin composite tube. The minimum SSCF has been found in this test program at 3.1 kN with a composite tube tested quasi-statically on the 6 mm triggering mechanism without pressurisation. The upper level of SSCF absorbing high impact energy is achievable by increasing the internal pressure of the specimen. A significant increment of energy absorption has been observed in the specimens crushed at 18 bar pressurisation on a 6 mm triggering mechanism, with 60% and 55% improvements, respectively for quasi-static and high speed tests, when compared to those tests without pressurisation. In order to determine theoretically the upper SSCF level, a simple calculation was performed. Woven fabric lay-up was used for the composite tube, thus the tensile strength is used in Eq. 1 for strength in the hoop direction.

Fig. 4. Pressure behaviour during the tests: (L) quasi-static, (R) high speed.

Fig. 5. Load displacement curves at different pressurisation levels with 6 mm trigger mechanism: (L) quasi-static, (R) high speed.

The maximum internal pressure P can be calculated at 41.9 MPa (419 Bar) by substituting the thickness t and the radius r of the tube. With this calculated theoretical high pressure applied to the system, the overall upper SSCF level is able to be increased up to 48.0 kN which is 15.5 times of the tubes crushed without pressurisation on a 6 mm triggering mechanism and 3.93 times of the tubes even crushed on a straight triggering mechanism. Since only compressed air is added to the energy absorber, it indicates the potential that crashworthy performance can be improved significantly without introducing any weight penalty.

$$\sigma_{hoop} = \frac{Pr}{t} \quad (1)$$

The experiment results illustrated in Fig. 5 indicate that it is feasible to design a crushing element with the variable load concept demonstrated in Fig. 1(b). The results presented in this work also indicate the current crushing system has the capability of carrying in-service flight loads with suitable pressurisation applied.

In general, the SSCF and specific energy absorption for the specimens tested under high speed condition were higher than the same configuration tested under the quasi-static tests. Interestingly, the average energy absorption for the specimens tested in high speed range is higher than the same configuration tested under the quasi-static condition, but the improvement/range of each set of high speed test is lower. The ranges of SSCF for a composite tubes crushed on the straight triggering

mechanism were from 12.2 kN to 14.8 kN and 13.3kN to 15.8 kN respectively for the quasi-static and high speed tests. The improvements are 23% for the quasi-static test, whereas 16% for the high speed test. For the composite tubes tested on a 6.0 mm triggering mechanism, the improvements are 60% and 55% respectively for quasi-static and high speed tests.

5. Conclusion

An experimental investigation using energy absorbing pressurised composite tubes has been reported. In order to overcome the drawback of existing constant or fixed load energy absorbing systems, a novel variable load concept has been introduced. A crushing system based on a variable and controllable crushing load was designed and tested to verify the feasibility of the concept. The constant internal pressure was maintained during crushing without leakage. As expected, the specimens with 18 bar pressurisation showed the highest crushing load and best specific energy absorption performance. A 60% enhancement in the energy absorption capacity was realised compared with an unpressurised tube. The current study indicates a variable load range from 23% (experimentally) to 15.5 times (theoretically) of the baseline for a fixed load energy absorber is achievable. The concept and the results illustrate that an adaptable composite crushing element can be designed that will be fully expended under a range of impact scenarios. This means that the forces transmitted to the occupants can be minimized subject to achieving the required energy

absorption, thus significantly improving survivability.

Future work will focus on impact testing based on the current concept and the development of practical energy absorbing structures which can automatically set the variable load to absorb the vehicle's kinetic energy under crash loading conditions. This will involve the development of suitable crushing system with a quick response pressure regulator, which is capable of releasing the compressed air rapidly under realistic impact loading. With further development, an adaptive energy absorbing sub-floor structure could become an important component in the crash management system of the next generation of aerospace platforms.

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